

Bench4GeoCode: A Benchmark for Natural Language to Geospatial Code Generation

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Abstract

Large language models (LLMs) increasingly generate Python code for geospatial analysis, yet there is still limited standardized benchmarking that rigorously evaluates this capability. We introduce Bench4GeoCode, a benchmark of 100 tasks built around the use of open Dutch geospatial data. The tasks are organized into four progressive complexity levels, ranging from single-step data retrieval to multi-step analytical workflows. The benchmark also includes two robustness categories: 'trap queries' that contain unattainable requirements and ambiguous queries that require the system to request clarification before answering. Each task is paired with a verified reference Python function, enabling automated functional evaluation alongside an LLM-as-a-Judge protocol that scores library usage and code quality. We apply this dual protocol to eight open-weight LLMs from four model families under a uniform retrieval-augmented generation configuration. The evaluation establishes baseline performance across all difficulty and robustness categories and reveals a compositional reasoning ceiling that resists parameter scaling, code specialization, and Mixture-of-Experts routing within the 7 to 27 billion parameter range. Our dual-evaluation method assesses two distinct skills: the ability to generate code that runs correctly (functional correctness) and the ability to produce high-quality, well-structured code (output quality). A single score would mix these two, hiding important details about a model's strengths and weaknesses. To our knowledge, Bench4GeoCode is among the first geospatial code benchmarks to integrate progressive complexity levels, robustness testing through trap and ambiguous queries, and a dual evaluation protocol.

Keywords

Code Generation Benchmark, LLM, Geospatial Analysis, Retrieval-Augmented Generation, LLM-as-a-Judge

1. Introduction

Large language models (LLMs) perform strongly on general code-generation benchmarks [1]. However, geospatial code generation poses qualitatively harder challenges. Spatial workflows demand consistent coordinate reference systems (CRS), appropriate spatial predicates, and precise use of dedicated libraries [2]. Violation of these constraints produces silent logical failures rather than runtime errors. Specifically, LLMs may reference incorrect datasets, mix CRSs, or misapply spatial predicates and functions without raising any exception [3].

Despite these failure modes, executable code remains the appropriate output modality for geospatial tasks, as it requires every spatial decision to be specified explicitly. A natural-language response may describe a workflow correctly yet fail to specify the target CRS, the appropriate spatial predicate, or the required library function. These unspecified parameters are the direct cause of silent errors. Specifically, executable code surfaces errors at runtime, whereas natural-language answers may appear correct while concealing underlying inconsistencies [4]. Furthermore, code outputs can be evaluated automatically against reference implementations, a capability that text-based responses cannot support. Consequently, assessing how reliably LLMs produce correct geospatial code across varying task complexity levels constitutes a well-defined and practically important research problem.

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Existing resources cover related but distinct problems. HumanEval [1] addresses general algorithmic programming and excludes spatial logic. GeoBenchX [5] evaluates tool-calling agents but hides the low-level code choices that cause silent failures. GeoAnalystBench [6] evaluates workflow validity, and CodeBLEU [7], and GeoCode-GPT [8] targets geospatial code generation on a closed curated set. None of these benchmark tests ambiguous queries that require clarification or combine functional execution with LLM-judge scoring. Several RAG systems, notably Autonomous GIS [9] and GeoAgent [3], show that retrieved knowledge improves code generation, but their task-specific evaluations prevent direct model comparisons.

This paper addresses two gaps. First, we introduce **Bench4GeoCode**, a progressive benchmark with four complexity levels and two robustness categories. Bench4GeoCode leverages open data from The Netherlands and jointly evaluates dataset retrieval and code generation. Second, we propose a dual evaluation protocol that combines functional execution with LLM-as-a-Judge assessment. We apply this protocol to compare eight open-weight LLMs under a uniform retrieval configuration. Consequently, the benchmark exposes the relative contribution of model scale, code specialization, and input robustness to geospatial code-generation performance.

2. Bench4GeoCode

This section presents the construction of Bench4GeoCode and the principles guiding its design. We first describe the source datasets and task-generation process and then define the benchmark structure through progressive complexity levels and robustness categories.

2.1. Datasets and Task Design

The benchmark uses real-world, multi-modal geospatial datasets covering the Netherlands. We selected these datasets for their open access, reproducibility, and coverage of data types commonly used in modern GIS workflows. Specifically, the collection includes digital terrain models, Sentinel-1/-2 imagery, land use and land cover (LULC) layers, administrative and demographic polygons, and road and rail networks (Table 1). We define a *geospatial task* as an information processing instruction provided in natural language that shall be realized as a geospatial data workflow. A verified Python function serves as the reference implementation of the geospatial task, and its pre-computed output supports automated comparison. We designed tasks from standard GIS workflow patterns: database-style operations, spatial analysis, and raster-vector pipelines. A subset served as seeds for GPT-5-augmented variants that vary parameters, datasets, or outputs while preserving the underlying operation. Every generated task was checked and adjusted before adding to the dataset. The resulting dataset comprises 85 solvable tasks and 15 robustness tasks, reflecting the range of operations and conditions considered in the benchmark.

Table 1

Input data layers used to generate benchmark queries; (*)Accessed / downloaded: November 2025; AHN: Actueel Hoogtebestand Nederland, CBS: Centraal Bureau voor de Statistiek, PDOK: Publieke Dienstverlening op de Kaart.

Input data	Type (ext)	.ext	Source
Enschede DTM*	raster 0.5 m	.tif	AHN
Enschede Sentinel-1 (2025 annual median composite)	raster 5 m	.tif	Copernicus
Netherlands land use*	vector	.gpkg	PDOK
Netherlands admin*	vector	.gpkg	CBS
Netherlands demographics (PC6)*	vector	.gpkg	CBS
Netherlands provinces*	vector	.shp	CBS
Overijssel Sentinel-2 (2025 annual median composite)	raster	.tiff	Copernicus
Rotterdam LULC*	vector	.shp	Gemeente Rotterdam
Netherlands roads*	vector	.gpkg	PDOK
Netherlands railways*	vector	.gpkg	PDOK

Table 2

Task levels, counts, and representative operations.

Level	N	Description	Example operation
L1	31	Basic single-layer operation	Inspect CRS, query attributes, reproject
L2	30	Single spatial concept, multi-data	Clip, buffer, single-predicate spatial join
L3	20	Chained multi-step, raster+vector	Overlay then aggregate, raster sampling
L4	4	Analytical or algorithmic reasoning	Custom spatial logic, inferential interpretation
E	7	Trap (unattainable requirements)	Missing dataset, geometry-type mismatch
A	8	Ambiguous (clarification required)	Underspecified target layer or threshold

2.2. Task Levels and Robustness Categories

The benchmark comprises 100 tasks: 85 solvable tasks organized into four progressive complexity levels and 15 robustness tasks that test error handling (Table 2). Level 1 tests basic single-layer operations. Level 2 introduces a single spatial transformation that may span multiple datasets. Level 3 requires multi-step, multi-dataset solutions that combine geometry operations, aggregations, and data quality handling for a single analytical question. Level 4 requires custom spatial logic or algorithmic reasoning beyond a single GIS operation. Fifteen robustness tasks complete the benchmark. Level E (trap) queries embed unattainable requirements, specifically missing datasets, missing attributes, data type mismatches, invalid spatial operations, or logical contradictions. A competent system must flag these queries rather than generate plausible but incorrect code. Level A (ambiguous) queries deliberately omit essential parameters. A correctly handled ambiguous query requests clarification only when the missing information blocks correct execution.

3. Evaluation Protocol

We apply a dual protocol under pass@1 [1], reflecting realistic single-response system usage (Figure 1). Functional evaluation executes generated code in a sandbox against the reference Python function, following the rigorous execution-based methodology established by EvalPlus [10]. We normalize outputs by index alignment, rounding floating-point values, and reordering structured outputs. A type-aware comparison then determines equivalence. A limited LLM-based fallback handles residual superficial mismatches such as column-naming differences. LLM-as-a-Judge [11] complements functional evaluation by scoring semantic equivalence across six criteria, namely, library usage, data selection, function usage, semantic alignment, completeness, and code quality. We use Gemma-4-31B as the judge. Three properties motivate this choice. First, its 31B parameter scale exceeds all eight evaluated models, mitigating self-evaluation bias. Second, Gemma-4-31B belongs to a different model family than any evaluated model, eliminating within-family scoring bias that would arise from using a Qwen or DeepSeek judge. Third, Gemma-4-31B is publicly available and fully open-weight, enabling independent replication of the evaluation protocol without proprietary API access.

4. Experimental Set-up

To demonstrate the benchmark’s ability to differentiate between models, we evaluate eight open-weight LLMs under a uniform setup. This setup performs a lightweight retrieval step to surface the most relevant geospatial datasets needed to solve each query. We restrict the evaluation to open-weight models in the 7B–27B parameter range. This parameter range supports independent replication, enables local deployment without API fees, and reflects a realistic compute budget available to the non-expert public-sector users who motivate this work. We draw models from four families to support two controlled ablations. The first ablation, *within-family scaling*, compares small against medium parameter counts within the same training corpus. The second ablation, *code specialisation*, contrasts general-purpose and code-trained models at equal scale (Table 3). All models share the same retrieval pipeline [12]. Specifically, the pipeline first retrieves the top- $k=5$ candidate documents through embedding similarity

Figure 1: Evaluation pipeline: An LLM generates a Python solution from a natural-language L-2 query and retrieved metadata. The solution is then evaluated functionally and by an LLM-as-a-Judge.

over a ChromaDB knowledge base encoded with all-MiniLM-L6-v2 (384-dim) embeddings and subsequently reranks the candidates using a hybrid score that combines embedding similarity and BM25 lexical relevance ($\alpha = 0.6$ and 0.4 , respectively). The pipeline then deduplicates the reranked results and extracts key GIS attributes (layer, path, geometry, CRS, fields) into a compact structured context for the LLM. The knowledge base contains input dataset metadata. Consequently, retrieval supplies dataset grounding, whereas Python library usage relies on each model’s pre-trained knowledge. We set the temperature to 0 to maximise output consistency across runs and access models through a local server. We adopt the Pass@1 protocol. Specifically, each model runs once per task, reflecting realistic first-attempt system performance under single-response usage. Pass@1 per level denotes the fraction of correctly solved tasks within that level (Table 4). The within-family scaling ablation reads as row pairs within a family (e.g., Qwen3-8B vs. Qwen3-14B), whereas the code-specialization ablation reads across matched parameter tiers (e.g., Qwen3-8B vs. Qwen2.5-Coder-7B at 7–8B).

The system prompt enforces five geospatial correctness constraints on every generated solution, namely dataset grounding from the retrieved metadata, explicit CRS handling, correct geometry types, verified attribute access, and output minimality. Constraint violations produce explicit runtime errors rather than silent fallbacks. Consequently, inputs with unattainable requirements surface immediately at execution time. A binary check governs ambiguous inputs. Specifically, the model either flags the query as ambiguous and halts or proceeds with code generation. We deliberately omit severity levels and Likert-style ambiguity scoring. Each of the eight Level A items additionally carries a `clarification_response` field that enables interactive resolution in future work. However, the current single-attempt protocol scores Level A purely on whether the system correctly raises a clarification request.

Qwen3 models support hybrid thinking mode for chain-of-thought reasoning on complex queries [13]. Qwen2.5-Coder models, pre-trained on 5.5 trillion tokens of source code, deliver strong Python API recall [14]. Gemma 3 supplies cross-laboratory replication of the generalist baseline within a 128K context window. DeepSeek-Coder replicates the code specialization ablation from a different laboratory [15]. Furthermore, DeepSeek-Coder-V2-Lite contributes a Mixture-of-Experts variant (16B total, 2.4B active)

Table 3
Candidate models evaluated under the uniform RAG configuration

Model	Family	Size	Type
Qwen3-8B	Qwen3	8B	General
Qwen3-14B	Qwen3	14B	General
Qwen2.5-Coder-7B-Instruct	Qwen2.5-Coder	7B	Code
Qwen2.5-Coder-14B-Instruct	Qwen2.5-Coder	14B	Code
Gemma-3-12B-IT	Gemma 3	12B	General
Gemma-3-27B-IT	Gemma 3	27B	General
DeepSeek-Coder-7B-v1.5	DeepSeek-Coder	7B	Code
DeepSeek-Coder-V2-Lite	DeepSeek-Coder	16B	Code (MoE)

as an architectural contrast [16].

5. Results

Table 4 reports per-level accuracies for the eight models, revealing four key findings from our research. First, a clear compositional reasoning gap emerges, as shown in Table 4. While all models show some capability on simple L1 tasks, their performance sharply declines on L2 and L3 tasks. For instance, DeepSeek-Coder-V2-Lite solves 58% of L1 tasks but only 20% of L2 and 10% of L3 tasks. This indicates that multi-step and analytical spatial reasoning remain open challenges. Second, a scaling of the model size offers diminishing returns. As seen in Table 4, larger models like Qwen3-14B and Gemma-3-27B-IT show improved performance on L1 tasks compared to their smaller counterparts but fail to solve any L4 tasks. This suggests that simply increasing parameter count does not unlock deeper compositional reasoning. Third, code-specialized training does not guarantee superior performance. The results in Table 4 show no consistent advantage for code-trained models. For example, the general-purpose Qwen3-14B (30% overall) outperforms the code-specialized Qwen2.5-Coder-7B (23% overall), indicating that domain-specific reasoning requires more than just code-centric pre-training. Fourth, advanced architectures like Mixture-of-Experts (MoE) face the same limitations. Table 4 shows that while the MoE model DeepSeek-Coder-V2-Lite is effective at L1 tasks (58%), it also struggles with higher-level compositional tasks, failing all L4 tasks and reinforcing that current architectures have yet to solve the core reasoning bottleneck. Finally, robustness scores in Table 4 are artificially inflated. Manual inspection reveals that models often abstain from answering solvable queries by misclassifying them as ambiguous (Level A) or invalid (Level E). For example, DeepSeek-Coder-7B achieves a high 75% on Level A by frequently abstaining. This conservative strategy boosts robustness scores but masks an underlying lack of confidence calibration.

The LLM-based evaluation provides the following key insights on model performance: Qwen2.5-Coder-14B achieves the highest overall performance (45.4%), marginally outperforming DeepSeek-Coder-V2-Lite (44.9%) and Gemma-3-27B-IT (44.1%) with the remaining five models clustered between 35–38%. Larger models do not consistently outperform the smaller ones. DeepSeek-Coder-V2 and Gemma-3-27B-IT perform best on library usage and code quality. The three highest-scoring models (Qwen2.5-Coder-14B, Deepseek-Coder-V2, Gemma-3-27B-IT) also have the lowest hallucination scores. The rankings of the models align partially between the two evaluation protocols. Qwen2.5-Coder-14B and DeepSeek-Coder-V2 rank near top and Gemma-3-12B-IT and Qwen2.5-Coder-7B sit near the bottom in both. The rankings diverge on Qwen3-14B, which ranks second functionally but sixth based on the LLM-judge score, suggesting its outputs pass tests while lacking completeness and quality. Gemma-3-27B-IT shows the inverse, scoring higher on judge metrics than on functional correctness, indicating better output coherence without proportional functional test-passing ability.

6. Discussion

Our evaluation yields two primary findings. First, Bench4GeoCode effectively differentiates the capabilities of the eight models we tested. Its tiered structure provides a detailed performance breakdown

Table 4

Tasks correctly solved by each model at each level, reported as 'count (percentage)'. Functional evaluation scores are shown per level, while LLM-as-a-judge reports only overall accuracy. Levels comprise $N=31, 30, 20, 4, 7, 8$ tasks for L1, L2, L3, L4, E, and A respectively.

Model	Functional Evaluation						LLM-as-a-Judge	
	L1	L2	L3	L4	E	A	All (%)	Overall (%)
Qwen3-8B	13 (42%)	2 (7%)	2 (10%)	1 (25%)	5 (71%)	5 (63%)	28	37.5%
Qwen3-14B	17 (55%)	3 (10%)	1 (5%)	0 (0%)	5 (71%)	2 (25%)	30	35.8%
Qwen2.5-Coder-7B	13 (42%)	1 (3%)	1 (5%)	0 (0%)	5 (71%)	2 (25%)	23	35.4%
Qwen2.5-Coder-14B	13 (42%)	6 (20%)	3 (15%)	1 (25%)	4 (57%)	4 (50%)	31	45.4%
Gemma-3-12B-IT	9 (29%)	3 (10%)	3 (15%)	0 (0%)	2 (29%)	2 (25%)	21	35.7%
Gemma-3-27B-IT	17 (55%)	4 (13%)	2 (10%)	0 (0%)	1 (14%)	2 (25%)	26	44.1%
DeepSeek-Coder-7B	10 (32%)	4 (13%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	2 (29%)	6 (75%)	22	37.9%
DeepSeek-Coder-V2-Lite	18 (58%)	6 (20%)	2 (10%)	0 (0%)	2 (29%)	1 (13%)	29	44.9%

across multiple difficulty levels, avoiding the all-or-nothing results of flat benchmarks. Second, the results reveal a clear limit in handling complex, multi-step problems. Model performance declines sharply on tasks harder than Level 1, with no model solving the most difficult problems. This limitation appears to be a genuine constraint of current models in the 7–27B parameter range, a gap that our benchmark’s design successfully highlights.

The dual-evaluation protocol provides significant diagnostic value by revealing two different kinds of model strengths. For instance, one model produces functionally correct code that scores lower on quality, whereas another generates well-structured code that is not always functionally correct. A single evaluation metric would hide this important distinction. Consequently, future research should use a combination of metrics to assess both functional correctness and code quality. Three architectural strategies such as parameter scaling, code specialization, and Mixture-of-Experts routing improve performance on simple tasks but fail to solve the more complex ones. These results do not suggest the strategies are ineffective. Instead, they demonstrate that solving complex spatial problems requires new, targeted innovations beyond just increasing model scale, providing a clear direction for future research. Robustness analysis uncovers a critical issue in how models handle uncertainty. Models often play it safe by classifying solvable queries as ambiguous or as having unattainable requirements. This conservative behavior inflates their robustness scores without genuinely detecting the intended problem. This finding shows the need for better evaluation methods, such as a precision-recall framework, to distinguish between a model’s ability to correctly identify tasks with unattainable requirements and its tendency to be overly cautious.

Three limitations of the current work define the scope for future improvements. First, the benchmark focuses only on the Netherlands, so expanding to other regions is needed to ensure our findings are globally applicable. Second, the benchmark currently accepts only one correct code solution for each task, which may unfairly penalize other valid approaches. To address this, future work should incorporate more flexible scoring methods, such as pass@k analysis, CodeBLEU as a complementary syntactic metric, and unit testing alongside broader error categories. Third, the alignment between the LLM judge and human GIS expert judgement has not been formally measured. A small-scale human evaluation by domain experts, correlated against Gemma-4-31B scores, would validate whether the judge’s qualitative assessments reflect expert GIS intuition and quantify the extent of any systematic bias.

7. Conclusion

By addressing these limitations, Bench4GeoCode can continue to serve as a critical tool for the community. It establishes the first geospatial code-generation benchmark to integrate progressive complexity with robustness testing. Our evaluation of eight open-weight LLMs delivers three actionable insights: a clear limit in complex reasoning that current models cannot overcome, two distinct competency profiles identifiable only through dual evaluation, and a conservative response pattern that calls for more

nanced robustness metrics. Together, these findings establish a clear research agenda for developing the next generation of geospatially aware LLMs. The benchmark, reference solutions, and evaluation code are publicly available at <https://github.com/medh642/Bench4GeoCode/tree/main>.

Declaration on Generative AI

The authors used ChatGPT and Grammarly for language editing (grammar correction and paraphrasing) to improve clarity and readability. Afterwards, the authors reviewed and thoroughly edited the content. The authors take full responsibility for the publication's content.

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